

Hedgehog: A Versatile Controller for Educational Robotics

Markus Klein, *klein@pria.at*
Practical Robotics Institute, Austria

Clemens Koza, *koza@pria.at*
Practical Robotics Institute, Austria

Wilfried Lepuschitz, *lepuschitz@pria.at*
Practical Robotics Institute Austria

Gottfried Koppensteiner, *koppensteiner@pria.at*
Practical Robotics Institute Austria

Abstract

We describe Hedgehog, an educational robotics controller designed to foster interest in STEM subjects. Hedgehog allows building robots out of common actuators and sensors, and can be combined with Lego for a beginner-friendly experience. Through building robots, students can learn and apply engineering, electronics, planning and teamwork skills. The controller facilitates learning programming at different age levels through both textual and visual programming support. For advanced students, Hedgehog's open source ecosystem allows delving into subjects such as microcontroller programming or cooperative robots as well. Hedgehog has been used in numerous workshops and also in robotics competitions with great success.

Keywords

Robotics; programming; visual programming; STEM

Hedgehog Controller

Hedgehog is a robotics controller: a computer aimed at controlling robotic components to allow building and programming robots. It is general-purpose, meaning that it was designed not only for a single task but to support whatever robotic project one might envision, and designed with educational use cases in mind. For example, Hedgehog controllers connect to a central WiFi, meaning that network congestion is less of a problem even in classrooms with multiple robots.

The Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller was designed to offer learning capabilities for people of different ages and skill levels. As Hedgehog itself is only the controller, a lot of its features relate to software development, but also the hardware was designed with this in mind. The Raspberry Pi utilized by Hedgehog allows for experimentation, and connectors of the Pi and microcontroller not directly used for Hedgehog's core functionality are accessible as well. The case exposes the Pi's USB, HDMI, SD card slot, etc., and has holing compatible to Lego to allow children to build robots out of familiar components. Although mechanically compatible with Lego, Lego's motors and sensors are not supported due to their proprietary plugs. Instead, Hedgehog uses standard 0.1" pin headers and is compatible to easily available and relatively cheap RC-Servos.

Software Platform

Hedgehog supports out-of-the-box text-based programming with Python as well as a visual programming environment based on Google's open source library Blockly. Especially the latter

Figure 1. Screenshot of the visual programming environment with the visual program on the left and the generated Python code on the right.

Figure 2. Hedgehog robotics controller in use at a robotics competition.

option allows beginners without any prior experience to dive into the world of robotics as it introduces an easier entry and less error potential in comparison with a text-based language. The design concept of the controller puts much emphasis on extensibility and versatility. Thus, adding new programming languages or integrating third-party libraries is well supported.

In order to allow children to quickly and easily get started with programming the Hedgehog controller, a web-based development environment called the Hedgehog IDE was implemented.

Programs are stored on the controller and users simply use their computers or tablets to connect to the controller via a browser and do not need to install any software on their machines which is a big advantage in workshop situations where time is always precious.

Real-World Usage

The Hedgehog controller has been used in a number of contexts, including workshops for middle school aged students, extracurricular activities with minimal supervision, and robotics tournaments. The controller was also used in the construction of an underwater robot, described in Grabler et al. (2018), which was in turn used in multiple educational robotics activities. Anecdotal evidence from these activities hints towards good acceptance of the Hedgehog system with regard to hardware compatibility (electronics connectors and mechanical connection points), usability of the development environment described in the previous section, and programming means - the libraries and the Python and Blockly languages.

For a subset of activities, in particular four workshops with 70 students aged 11 to 16, Koza et al. (2017) analyzed quantitatively and compared them with four earlier workshops using different controllers. All eight workshops were part of the same project and used a comparable style and setting. The reference workshops' controllers used the C programming language instead of Python.

The statements "working with robots was interesting/difficult/fun," and "overall, I would rank this course with ... stars," were looked at. Regarding difficulty, the results showed no significant difference. In the other categories (interesting, fun, overall stars), low ratings (1 or 2 stars) were almost absent from the Hedgehog workshops' results, while they did show up more frequently in the reference workshops. Although factors such as different instructors and students were not taken into account, it can be interpreted that students were more engaged in the workshops using Hedgehog.

Conclusion

Hedgehog shows a lot of promise for the education domain and has already been used successfully in different settings. We are confident that Hedgehog's ease of use and versatility makes it a good choice for various educational use cases. Through this, the Hedgehog controller helps reaching diverse audiences to foster their STEM interests.

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Demonstration

During this 30-minute demonstration, we will present the Hedgehog educational robotics controller, including its hardware capabilities and the software platform. The demonstration will also introduce means to facilitate constructionist learning by building and programming robots using the controller.

References

- Koza, C., Wolff, M., Frank, D., Lepuschitz, W. and Koppensteiner, G. (2017) Architectural Overview and Hedgehog in Use. In Proceedings: International Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2017. p. 238-249.
- Reinhard Grabler, Markus Klein, Thomas Fellner, and Gottfried Koppensteiner. (2018) Development of a Low-Cost Maritime Educational Robotics Platform. *International Journal of Materials, Mechanics and Manufacturing*, Vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 208-214.